

Noise Texture Augmentation Improves Pediatric Generalizability in Deep Learning CT Denoising Models

Running Title: Pediatric CT Noise Texture Augmentation

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1 ABSTRACT

2 **Background:** Deep learning (DL) denoising models have been shown to be effective at reducing noise in
3 computed tomography (CT) images, enabling low dose acquisitions that are essential for pediatric
4 imaging. However, these DL models are primarily trained on adult patient image data, putting their
5 performance in pediatric patients in question due to key differences in pediatric anatomy, pathology,
6 and acquisition protocol.

7 **Purpose:** This study aims to take key image quality features from pediatric CT protocols that are missing
8 from adult protocols, notably coarser noise textures from sampling physically smaller fields of view, and
9 incorporate them into denoising model training using data augmentation techniques.

10 **Methods:** Using simulations, uniform phantoms with diameters ranging from the mean effective
11 diameter of newborns to adolescents were repeatedly scanned and reconstructed with body-fitting
12 fields of view (FOV)s. Taking the difference of these repeat images yields noise images with noise
13 textures characteristic of each phantom size. Patches from these size-specific noise images were then
14 added to the low noise target images of the adult patient training dataset to make new noise texture
15 augmented training pairs. RED-CNN denoising models were trained with and without noise texture
16 augmentation and performance was evaluated using objective and task-based image quality
17 assessments for pediatric denoising generalizability.

18 **Results:** The baseline RED-CNN denoising model trained on adult patient data achieved a mean noise
19 reduction of 78% in adult patients and 45% in newborn patients. Following noise texture augmented
20 training on the same dataset, a mean noise reduction of 73% was achieved in adults and 65% in
21 newborns, with the performance gap reduced from 33% to just 8% between adult and newborn patient
22 sizes. In addition, there was an overall increase in noise reduction averaged across all investigated
23 patient sizes, 70% with augmented training compared to 60% without. This improved pediatric
24 generalizability for a small cost in adult performance supports noise texture augmentation as a
25 regularization technique that reduces overfitting in adult-only trained denoising models. Furthermore,
26 task-based performance showed similar trends with the greatest low contrast detectability
27 improvement in infants as measured by a Channelized Hotelling model observer with an area under the
28 receiver operator characteristic curve (AUC) of 0.84 with augmented training compared to 0.80 without.

29 **Conclusion:** Due to scarcity of pediatric radiology exams and their protected status, pediatric training
30 data is and will likely remain scarce. However, this study has demonstrated that characterizing the
31 causes of poor performance in pediatric patients can yield insights into improved model training. By
32 augmenting model training with noise textures from pediatric protocol phantom scans image quality
33 and task-based performance were improved in newborns, infants, and small children not typically
34 available in training datasets. These findings support the use of noise texture data augmentation as a
35 regularization technique to improve generalizability and overall performance across a wider variety of
36 patient sizes than the model was originally trained with.

37 1 INTRODUCTION

38 Despite the rapid rise of artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) in radiology,¹ few devices
39 are developed or tested for pediatric patients.² To address this gap in technical development, new
40 campaigns like [Image IntelliGently™](#) aim to raise awareness about the need to develop and evaluate
41 AI/ML devices thoughtful of the unique needs and characteristics of pediatric patients.³

42 Dose reduction in x-ray computed tomography (CT) is particularly important for pediatric patients⁴ and
43 recently has been pursued in adults using deep learning (DL)-based image reconstruction and denoising
44 models to maintain diagnostic image quality at reduced x-ray dose.⁵ The performance of DL denoisers
45 has been shown to be advantageous to other advanced reconstruction methods like model-based
46 iterative reconstruction (MBIR) due to faster computation times, preferable noise texture, along with
47 comparable noise reduction and sharpness preservation.⁶ These DL denoisers are applied to images
48 following image reconstruction and are trained on many examples of paired low and high noise patient
49 images. However due to the scarcity of pediatric data in public datasets, development and testing of DL-
50 based CT image denoising and reconstruction in pediatrics is limited.⁷ Thus while DL-based image
51 denoising and reconstruction may be promising for pediatric CT dose reduction, there is a shortage of
52 studies evaluating their efficacy and generalizability in this population.

53 A limitation of deep learning techniques is their limited ability to generalize to data characteristically
54 different than they were trained with. Deep learning CT denoising models specifically have been shown
55 to be sensitive to changes in noise texture due to differences in reconstruction kernel and reconstructed
56 field of view (FOV).^{8,9} Noise texture refers to the visual appearance of noise that can be characterized by
57 its noise power spectrum. Zeng et al., 2022 demonstrated DL denoisers are sensitive to changes in noise
58 texture, behaving like band-pass filters, only removing noise from the range of spatial frequencies in the
59 training set.⁹ A negative consequence of this band-pass behavior is the potential for reduced
60 performance in imaging pediatric patients where pediatric protocols often require smaller reconstructed
61 FOVs with different noise textures.¹⁰

62 In other deep learning applications where the training dataset is small and does not capture the full
63 variability of the intended use population, data augmentation is one strategy to improve
64 generalizability. Data augmentation works by assuming that the variability of certain features in the
65 intended population can be modeled and incorporated into model training. Recently image-based
66 augmentations specific to CT have been introduced to improve generalizability of DL lung nodule
67 detection across a range of acquisition techniques by modeling noise properties expected in lower dose
68 acquisitions.¹¹

69 This work introduces noise texture augmentation, a data augmentation to improve deep learning CT
70 denoising performance in pediatric patients with waist sizes smaller than included in the adult training
71 dataset. Noise texture augmentation works by extracting noise textures from pediatric protocol scans of
72 pediatric-sized phantoms to augment denoising model training. The result is a denoising model that
73 generalizes better to smaller patients, saving time, resources, and radiation exposure compared to
74 compiling large datasets of pediatric patients, which is generally not feasible.

75 2 METHODS

76 This investigation starts by defining noise texture augmentation and the process of extracting noise
77 textures from pediatric protocol CT scans for augmenting training along with suggestions for selecting
78 augmentation strength. Experiments were performed to assess the impact of noise texture
79 augmentation on denoising pediatric images. These experiments include training DL denoising models
80 with and without noise texture augmentation using an adult dataset followed by assessments of
81 objective and task-based measures of image quality on pediatric-sized geometric and anthropomorphic
82 phantoms. Both simulated and physical scan data was used to support the study's conclusions.

83 2.1 NOISE TEXTURE AUGMENTATION

84 Noise texture augmented training differs from traditional denoising model training (Figure 1a) where
85 convolutional neural network (CNN) models are trained using low dose (LD), noisy, training patches as
86 inputs and full dose (FD), low noise, CT image patches as training target patches.¹² The model processes
87 the noisy input image yielding an estimated low noise image that is compared to the target low noise
88 image using the loss function to update the model weights and improve the estimates. As these training
89 inputs and targets generally are from adult protocol CT images, this approach works well in adults of
90 similar size and acquisition as in the training set, but has been shown to perform worse in pediatric
91 patients with smaller reconstructed fields of view (FOV).^{8,9} This performance degradation has been
92 shown to be due to the lower frequency noise texture associated with pediatric protocols.¹⁰ These lower
93 frequency, coarser noise textures, in pediatric CT arise from the smaller physical FOV sampled with the
94 same system spatial resolution as in larger adult scans.

95 Noise texture augmentation, summarized in Figure 1b, is a form of data augmentation which
96 compensates for the noise texture variability in pediatric protocol data that is missing from adult
97 training datasets. Here, noise texture patches from pediatric protocol CT are added to full dose training
98 targets to make new training examples, referred to as augmented inputs in Figure 1b. These augmented
99 inputs are batched together with the original low dose training inputs making up a proportion $\lambda \in [0, 1]$
100 of the total training data. This proportion λ controls the amount of augmentation, while the parameters
101 of the noise patch generation such as FOV and kernel influence the characteristics of noise that are
102 being augmented into the training routine.

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

103 Figure 1 Schematic diagrams of image-based deep learning CT denoising model training. (a) Traditional model training where
 104 training input patches are input to a model to make a prediction that is compared against the training target using the loss
 105 function to update the model. (b) In noise texture augmented training noise patches are added to the low noise training target
 106 to make new augmented inputs. While training, a proportion λ of the training data mini batch is from the augmented inputs
 107 while the remaining $1 - \lambda$ is from the original low dose training inputs. LD = Low dose, FD = Full dose CT acquisitions.

108 2.2 NOISE TEXTURE PATCHES

109 While the noise patches in Figure 1b could be derived from pediatric patient data using noise insertion
 110 methods,¹³ this work assumes that such pediatric data is unavailable for model training and
 111 demonstrates how phantom data is sufficient for making these noise patches for noise texture
 112 augmentation. The method for generating these noise texture patches is summarized in Figure 2a.
 113 Phantoms with diameters spanning the range of effective diameters expected in newborns to
 114 adolescents (Table 1) are selected and repeatedly scanned with tube current modulation to achieve an
 115 approximately constant noise index (Figure 2b) and avoid photon starvation artifacts in larger phantom
 116 sizes. Taking the difference of these repeat scans yields noise images with noise textures specific to each
 117 phantom size and the corresponding scan parameters (Figure 2c).

118 The noise only images are then histogram equalized such that the noise magnitude, defined as the pixel
 119 intensity standard deviation of each noise image, matches the training set noise, approximated by taking
 120 the difference of a sample of matched low and high noise training patches (Figure 2d). Histogram
 121 equalization can yield more stable and consistent model training but is only necessary if the noise
 122 magnitude of the phantom noise images is substantially different from the training set. This ensures that
 123 the augmented inputs have a similar noise magnitude as the original low dose training inputs.

124 Finally, patches are sampled from random locations across these noise images (example patches shown
 125 as inset images in Figure 2c), yielding size-specific noise texture patches with a range of noise textures
 126 (Figure 2e) representative of scans in each pediatric subgroup of Table 1. The size of the patches to be

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

127 used for augmented training is determined by the matrix size of the training examples (Figure 1), which
 128 can be small patches (e.g. 32×32 voxels), whole images, or even a 3 dimensional stack of images.

129
 130 *Figure 2 Noise patch generation for noise texture augmentation. a) Summary of size-specific noise patch generation which starts*
 131 *with collecting phantoms of diameter spanning the range of expected pediatric size (Table 1), these phantoms are scanned*
 132 *repeatedly with tube current modulation to achieve similar noise indices in different phantom sizes and reconstructed with body*
 133 *fitting fields of view b). Subtracting the consecutive repeat scans yields size-specific noise images c.). Histogram matching*
 134 *the phantom noise images to the training set noise images d) – found by taking the difference of a sample of matched low dose*
 135 *and high dose training patches – ensures that the augmented inputs (Figure 1) have the same noise magnitude as the low dose*
 136 *training inputs. The result are noise patches of similar noise magnitude as the training set but with range of noise textures*
 137 *represented by noise power peaks at different spatial frequencies e).*

Subgroup	Age Range	Waist Diameter Range
Newborn	≤ 1 mo	≤ 11.5 cm
Infant	> 1 mo & < 2 yrs	> 11.5 cm & ≤ 16.8 cm
Child	> 2 yrs & ≤ 12 yrs	> 16.8 cm & ≤ 23.2 cm
Adolescent	> 12 yrs & < 21 yrs	> 23.2 cm & < 34 cm
Adult	≥ 22 yrs	≥ 34 cm

138 *Table 1 Pediatric subgroups investigated defined by age range¹⁴ with representative effective waist diameters.¹⁵*

139 2.3 SELECTING AUGMENTATION STRENGTH λ

140 The augmentation strength parameter λ (Figure 1) sets the proportion of each training mini batch
 141 consisting of augmented inputs. For example, in a training batch size of 64 patches, $\lambda = 0.5$ would
 142 feature a batch with 32 augmented input patches and 32 original training input patches. The choice of λ
 143 was found by training different RED-CNN models with different augmentation strengths λ and
 144 measuring the standard deviation (std) in a central region of interest (ROI) from a validation set of

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

145 pediatric-sized uniform water images (Figure 3). For this study a λ that maximized noise reduction across
 146 the pediatric sizes was chosen. Thus, for the remainder of the investigation a $\lambda = 0.3$ RED-CNN
 147 augmented model was used as this augmentation strength achieved the minimum noise magnitude
 148 averaged across phantom sizes (11 – 35 cm) as shown in Figure 3.

149

150 *Figure 3 Selection of λ value from a central region of interest (ROI) standard deviation (std) measurement averaged across*
 151 *pediatric-sized uniform water phantom images from the validation dataset.*

152 2.4 EXPERIMENTS

153 To investigate the impact of noise texture augmentation on pediatric denoising, two image-based DL
 154 denoising models were trained, one with and the other without noise texture augmentation using the
 155 same model architecture and adult training dataset. Performance was assessed via simulation in each
 156 pediatric subgroup described in *Table 1* using noise magnitude and image sharpness as measures of
 157 objective image quality and a model observer-based low contrast detectability test as a measure of task-
 158 based image quality. Pediatric generalizability of these image quality measurements was assessed using
 159 a set of digital pediatric image quality (IQ) phantoms. Conclusions from the pediatric IQ phantoms were
 160 validated using a set of digital pediatric anthropomorphic phantoms¹⁶ and physical IQ phantom scans.

161 2.4.1 Denoising Model

162 An image-based RED-CNN DL denoising model architecture¹² was trained on 64×64 voxel patches of
 163 the Low Dose CT Grand Challenge Dataset (LDGC)¹⁷ using both the baseline training (Figure 1a) and noise
 164 texture augmentation (Figure 1b). The LDGC dataset is composed of abdominal non-contrast CT exams
 165 from 10 adult patients with reconstructed FOVs ranging from 34 – 42 cm in diameter summarized in
 166 Table 2. The dataset includes full- and quarter-dose image pairs for model training and validation. All 10
 167 patient exams were used for model development. Of these exams, 7 were used for updating model
 168 weights via training and the remaining 3 used for tuning hyperparameters such as learning rate,
 169 stopping point described previously,¹⁸ as well as selecting an augmentation strength of $\lambda = 0.3$ (Section
 170 2.3).

171

Dataset	Scanner	WED (cm) [Range, Mean]	Full-Dose Noise Index (HU)	kVp	FOV (cm) [Range, Mean]	Kernel
LDGC ⁷ (train)	Somatom Definition	25-35, 31	23	120	34-42, 38	D45
Pediatric IQ Phantoms ¹⁰ (test)	Virtual Somatom Definition	11-35, 20	23	120	12-36, 25	D45*
Anthropom orphic Phantoms ¹⁰ (test)	Virtual Somatom Definition	11-35, 21	23	120	12-39, 23	D45*
ACR464 (test)	Somatom Edge Plus	20	23	120	15, 25, 38**	Qr43***

172 *Table 2 Summary of datasets used for denoising model training and testing. This study focused on the Siemens scanners used in*
173 *the low dose CT grand challenge dataset (LDGC).¹⁷ The full dose noise index refers to the target noise level, measured in a water*
174 *ROI, achieved by varying x-ray tube output to account for patient size. *The reconstruction kernel used in simulations was a D45*
175 *equivalent kernel with the same 50% and 10% MTF cutoff values as the Siemens D45 kernel. **For ACR464 test data taken on the*
176 *Edge Plus scanner 3 FOVs were measured and all three are listed rather than their range and mean. ***The D45 kernel was no*
177 *longer available on the Somatom Edge Plus scanner used for making the physical validation test dataset so Qr43 was chosen*
178 *instead due to having similar noise and sharpness as D45. WED: Water equivalent diameter, FOV: Field of View.*

179 2.4.2 Image Quality Assessments

180 Denoising performance and pediatric generalizability was defined as image quality measured using a set
181 of digital pediatric image quality (IQ) phantoms to evaluate noise reduction and texture, image
182 sharpness, and low contrast detectability.¹⁰ These digital phantoms enable image denoising assessments
183 in a range of patient sizes spanning the range of pediatric subgroups defined in *Table 1*. For this study,
184 nine phantom diameters of each IQ phantom were uniformly sampled from the size range of 10-40 cm
185 diameter such that each pediatric subgroup was represented in the study.

186 Noise was measured as both noise magnitude and noise power spectra (NPS) in a uniform water
187 phantom simulated at different pediatric diameters. Noise magnitude measurements were calculated as
188 the standard deviation (std) of pixels in a central circular ROI in the uniform water phantom for each
189 phantom size with an ROI diameter equal to 40% the phantom diameter. NPS was measured using the
190 same process defined previously,¹⁰ where using the selected ROIs to calculate the complex modulus of
191 the 2D Fourier Transform of the ROI yielding the 2D NPS. These 2D NPS images were averaged across
192 200 repeat noise instances. 1D radially averaged NPS profiles were then extracted from these 2D NPS
193 images.

194 Image sharpness was assessed using the disk edge-based modulation transfer function (MTF)¹⁹ at eight
195 contrast levels using the cylindrical contrast inserts of the CTP404 densitometry module simulated in the
196 pediatric IQ phantoms.¹⁰ To minimize the effects of noise, the results of 10 repeat simulations were
197 averaged before making MTF measurements.

198 To assess the task-based performance of a DL denoiser in several pediatric subgroups, a low contrast
199 detectability study was performed with two mathematical model observers using the simulated MITA-
200 LCD phantom with low contrast inserts of 14, 7, 5, and 3 HU. These model observers were a Laguerre-
201 Gauss Channelized Hotelling observer (LG-CHO), an approximated ideal linear observer,²⁰ and a non-
202 prewhitening matched filter observer (NPW)²¹ known to be more responsive to noise reduction

203 strategies.⁶ For each investigated phantom diameter, signal-present and signal-absent images were each
204 simulated with 200 repeated acquisitions and then cropped around the low contrast insert. These linear
205 model observers utilize learned lesion template images and a few fit parameters, thus from this dataset
206 of paired signal-present and signal-absent ROIs, 40% are sufficient to train the linear model observers
207 and the remaining 60% were used for testing to evaluate detectability as a function of lesion size and
208 contrast level.

209 2.4.3 CT Simulations

210 In this study, phantom scan data for creating noise texture augmentation training patches (Figure 2) as
211 well as pediatric IQ phantom and pediatric anthropomorphic phantom test images were generated via
212 simulation. In these simulations, phantom definition, CT projections, and filtered backprojection (FBP)
213 reconstruction were all generated using the Michigan Image Reconstruction Toolbox (MIRT).²² The adult
214 protocol acquisition parameters were modeled after the Siemens CT scanner used in making the LDGC
215 dataset¹⁷ by matching the kVp, full dose noise index, and reconstruction kernel summarized in Table 2.
216 Poisson noise was simulated in the projections based on the mean number of photons reaching the
217 detector to create both full and quarter dose simulations with noise indices of 23 and 46 HU respectively
218 in central ROIs of a uniform water phantom, matching the noise index of the LDGC dataset. The pediatric
219 acquisition protocol differed from adult protocol based on abdomen/pelvis protocol recommendations
220 by the AAPM Alliance for Quality Computed Tomography.²³ Notably, the pediatric acquisitions were
221 reconstructed with the same body reconstruction kernel as the adult and body fitting FOV defined here
222 as 110% the patient effective diameter.

223 2.4.4 Digital Anthropomorphic and Physical Phantom Validations

224 Since the DL denoising models are trained on patient data rather than phantoms, the pediatric XCAT
225 cohort¹⁶ was included in the study validation to ensure that results found with the geometric pediatric-
226 sized IQ phantoms are representative of those to be expected in patients. In this anthropomorphic
227 validation experiment, noise reduction was measured both as a reduction in measured standard
228 deviation in liver ROIs as well as a reduction in root mean square error (RMSE) between the noisy
229 reconstructed images and the ground truth noiseless FBP.

230 Finally, to ensure that the conclusions drawn from simulations apply to real CT scan data, a physical
231 ACR464 phantom (Sun Nuclear) was repeatedly scanned on a physical CT scanner to compare noise
232 reduction trends with those measured in the simulation experiments. Images of the ACR phantom were
233 reconstructed at different FOVs to reproduce the noise textures at different sizes since only one
234 phantom size was available (Table 2). The dose levels in these scans were set to have similar noise
235 standard deviations to those in the quarter-dose LDGC CT scans.

236 3 RESULTS

237 The pediatric-sized IQ phantom assessment framework was used to assess the pediatric generalizability
238 of a RED-CNN DL denoising model trained on an adult dataset with and without noise texture
239 augmentation. Below are the physical image quality assessments and task-based low contrast
240 detectability results each reported as a function of patient size, followed by the validation experiment
241 results using digital anthropomorphic phantoms and physical scans of the ACR phantom.

242 3.1 DENOISING PERFORMANCE

243 Our first assessment compares noise reduction performance measured across digital phantoms with
 244 effective diameters ranging from newborn pediatric patients through adult, with anthropomorphic
 245 phantom examples of a newborn, child, and adult shown in Figure 4. By using automatic exposure
 246 control, implemented in the CT simulation framework, with a reference FBP noise level of 48 HU for the
 247 quarter dose acquisitions, all FBP reconstructions in Figure 4 have similar noise magnitude
 248 measurements taken from liver ROIs despite being of different diameter (27.6 and 11.2 cm diameter
 249 virtual adolescent and newborn patients shown), with the decreasing FOV size labeled on the y axis.
 250 Despite having similar noise magnitudes, the noise texture of the virtual newborn patient is coarser with
 251 a larger grain size. This reflects the limited spatial resolution of the imaging system when imaging with
 252 smaller voxel sizes which influences the noise texture.¹⁰ Following denoising with the baseline RED-CNN
 253 model, a negative correlation with size appears, as the measured noise magnitude in liver ROIs
 254 decreases with increasing effective diameter, from 25 HU in the newborn 11.2 cm diameter newborn
 255 down to 9 HU in the adult 34.2 cm diameter adult. However, this size dependence is no longer present
 256 in augmented training RED-CNN. After denoising with augmented RED-CNN model, all quarter dose FBP
 257 input images shown went from a measured noise magnitude of around 40 HU in the liver to
 258 approximately 10 HU, independent of size and FOV.

259
 260 *Figure 4 CT simulations of XCAT anthropomorphic phantoms of different effective diameter reconstructed with Filtered back*
 261 *projection (FBP) followed by denoising with different deep learning denoising models. Region of interest (ROI) measurements,*
 262 *shown as blue disk overlays, taken from the liver report pixel mean and standard deviation with the ROI. Display window, level:*
 263 *400, 40.*

264 These findings are supported by noise reduction measurements across all uniform and anthropomorphic
 265 phantom imaging simulations shown in Figure 5. Figure 5a shows noise reduction as measured by a
 266 reduction in standard deviation measured in both uniform liver ROIs in anthropomorphic phantoms (see
 267 examples in Figure 4) as well as 40% phantom diameter ROIs in uniform water phantoms. Following
 268 denoising with the baseline RED-CNN model, both uniform and anthropomorphic phantoms show the

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

269 lowest noise reduction in small phantom sizes. This baseline RED-CNN performance increases with
 270 phantom size and begins to plateau as test phantom diameter exceeds 25 cm which begins to overlap
 271 the patient diameters included in the LDGC training dataset range (Table 2). However, this patient size-
 272 dependence is less pronounced with the augmented RED-CNN noise reduction, especially when
 273 measured with the anthropomorphic test data where noise reduction is largely constant at 78% across
 274 all investigated phantom sizes. Note that the intersection of the baseline RED-CNN and augmented RED-
 275 CNN noise reduction curves is also at a patient effective diameter of 25 cm which is the start of the
 276 effective diameter range of the LDGC training dataset (Table 2).

277 Figure 5b presents noise reduction defined by root mean squared error (RMSE) reductions. These
 278 measurements reflect noise reduction across the whole image, rather than uniform ROIs measures
 279 shown in Figure 5a and include regions of different CT number and size such as the ribs, or boundaries
 280 between tissues. Comparing RMSE reductions shows the same trends of improved performance using
 281 the RED-CNN augmented model in smaller phantom sizes compared to the baseline RED-CNN. However
 282 the relative performance improvement is diminished when comparing RMSE reduction versus uniform
 283 region standard deviation reduction as RMSE also reflects the additional smoothing of edges and impact
 284 on image sharpness apparent on inspection of Figure 4 and as discussed later in Figure 7.

285

286 *Figure 5 Denoising efficiency as a function of phantom size with body fitting reconstructed field of view (FOV). a) Noise reduction*
 287 *performance defined as reduction of pixel intensity standard deviation (std) relative to filtered backprojection (fbp): noise std*
 288 *reduction [%] = [fbp std - denoised std]/fbp std × 100%. Noise in uniform phantoms is measured in central circular regions of*
 289 *interest (ROIs) 40% the phantom diameter. In anthropomorphic phantoms, the ROI size was set at 30% phantom effective diameter*
 290 *and only applied to slices where there was enough liver to fit the ROI, see Figure 4 for examples. b) Noise reduction performance*
 291 *defined as reduction in root mean squared error (rmse) with the ground truth simulated phantom: rmse reduction [%] = [fbp rmse*
 292 *– denoised rmse]/fbp rmse × 100%. RMSE reduction is measured across the whole image. Shaded regions around line profiles*
 293 *indicate 95% confidence intervals measured across 200 repeat simulations.*

294 By binning the phantoms based on diameter we can further breakdown this size-based performance in
 295 terms of pediatric subgroups (Table 1) as shown in Figure 6. The baseline RED-CNN denoising model
 296 trained on adult patient data achieved a mean noise reduction of 78% in adult patients and 45% in
 297 newborn patients. Following noise texture augmented training on the same dataset, a mean noise
 298 reduction of 73% was achieved in adults and 65% in newborns with an overall increase in noise

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

299 reduction averaged across all investigated patient sizes of 70% with augmented training compared to
 300 60% without.

301

302 *Figure 6 Denoising performance measured as pixel intensity standard deviation (std) measured in liver regions of interest (ROIs)*
 303 *from anthropomorphic phantoms. The ROI size was set at 30% phantom effective diameter and only applied to slices where*
 304 *there was enough liver to fit the ROI, see Figure 4 for examples. Pediatric subgroups are based on the waist diameters defined in*
 305 *Table 2.*

306 3.2 IMAGE SHARPNESS

307 The impact of denoisers on image sharpness is shown in Figure 7 as a relative reduction in the 50% and
 308 10% MTF cutoff frequencies, e.g. (Denoised image spatial frequency at 50% MTF)/(FBP spatial frequency
 309 at 50% MTF). The findings that image sharpness is constant across reconstructions at high contrast (990
 310 HU) and diminished at lower contrasts (-35 HU) is consistent with other studies of DL denoising.⁹
 311 Additionally, we see a greater reduction in sharpness in all subgroups except adults where the greatest
 312 difference from the original RED-CNN is observed in newborns. This can be interpreted that the original
 313 RED-CNN is not denoising as strongly in these smaller patient sizes and thus not impacting the image
 314 sharpness as much as the augmented model.

315

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

316

317 *Figure 7 Image sharpness evaluated as 50% and 10% cutoff frequencies of modulation transfer function (MTF) measured from*
 318 *radially averaged disk measurements at different contrast levels, shown as the title of each plot. Average MTF cutoffs values are*
 319 *shown for each pediatric subgroup based on phantom diameter (Table 1) with error bars representing the 95% bootstrap*
 320 *confidence interval. Relative MTF at x% = (Denoised image spatial frequency at x% MTF)/(FBP spatial frequency at x% MTF).*

321 **3.3 LOW CONTRAST DETECTABILITY**

322 Task-based image performance was assessed using a low contrast detectability test with the MITA low
 323 contrast detectability (MITA-LCD) phantom simulated across a range of pediatric diameters.¹⁰ Two
 324 different model observers were used to perform the detection task: a Laguerre-Gauss Channelized
 325 Hotelling Observer (LG-CHO) and a non-prewhitening (NPW) observer. Detection performance was
 326 assessed across different phantom sizes, lesion contrasts, and lesion diameters and denoising methods
 327 in Figure 8. Both observers measured an increase in detectability with phantom diameter in the baseline
 328 filtered back projection (FBP) reconstruction series as the noise spatial frequencies become higher
 329 frequency (Figure 2e). This increase in FBP detectability with phantom size has two causes. The first is
 330 due to the spatial frequencies of the image noise becoming more distinct from the low spatial frequency
 331 lesion. The second is that the lesion diameters also scale with phantom diameter. Beyond this FBP
 332 baseline, detectability was found to be most improved in the lowest contrast 3 HU, 10% diameter lesion
 333 following denoising by the augmented RED-CNN. This relative improvement was greatest when
 334 measured by a NPW observer which is consistent with previous studies that have shown NPW observers
 335 to be more sensitive to noise texture changes from denoisers.^{6,10} Measured detectability improvement
 336 was more modest when measured by the more conservative LG-CHO observer and was only present in
 337 the 3 HU lesion. Together these model observers provide reasonable bounds for low contrast
 338 detectability.²⁴

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

339

340 *Figure 8 Low contrast detectability area under the receiver operator characteristic curve (AUC) as a function of phantom*
 341 *diameter from quarter dose test images. Detectability is assessed using two model observers: a Laguerre-Gauss Channelized*
 342 *Hotelling observer (LG-CHO) and a non-prewhitening (NPW) observer. The 3 HU contrast lesion has a diameter of 10% the*
 343 *phantom diameter and the 14 HU diameter is 5% the phantom diameter.*

344 **3.4 VALIDATION WITH PHYSICAL PHANTOM DATA**

345 To further validate denoising trends with and without noise texture augmentation, the ACR464 phantom
 346 was imaged (Figure 9a) with a physical CT scanner (listed in Table 2 as ACR464). Figure 9b shows the
 347 uniform region of the ACR phantom reconstructed at three different FOVs to produce the voxel sizes
 348 and textures of an adult, child, and infant patient size. The noise reduction curves as a function of FOV
 349 sizes are plotted alongside the previously simulated uniform water phantom results in Figure 9c and
 350 Figure 9d. These physical scan results follow the same trends as the simulated results (Figure 9d)
 351 showing a trend with FOV that is less pronounced following data augmentation. There is a small
 352 negative bias in the physical results due to the difference in scanner model and recon kernel since the
 353 original LDGC kernel was no longer available on the validation scanner (Table 2).

354

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

355 Figure 9 Physical image quality (IQ) phantom scan validation experiment. a) Uniform region for noise assessment in physical
 356 ACR464 phantom scanned on a Siemens Edge Plus scanner (see Table 2 for details). b) ACR phantom reconstructed at 3 fields of
 357 view (FOVs) estimating adult, child, and infant scan conditions. c) Simulated images of uniform phantom defined at adult, child,
 358 and newborn size. d) Comparison of noise reduction trends measured in physical and simulated images. Display window width,
 359 window level: 150, 0.

360 **4 DISCUSSION**

361 This noise texture augmentation method for training pediatric generalizable denoising models with adult
 362 datasets was motivated by our previous study¹⁰ that such models generalize poorly in pediatric patients
 363 due to insufficient variability in FOV sizes represented in adult training datasets. This work introduced
 364 and characterized noise texture augmentation as a means of improving pediatric generalizability with
 365 limited adult-only training datasets. Noise texture augmentation consists of extracting noise textures
 366 from pediatric protocol CT scans that are added to routine dose adult protocol images to synthesize
 367 noisy pediatric images for augmented training (Figure 1b). This optimal augmentation strength was
 368 found to be at $\lambda = 0.3$ for our training data set and was the value used in the rest of the study. The
 369 resulting noise augmented RED-CNN model was then evaluated on pediatric denoising generalizability
 370 using pediatric-sized versions of standard image quality phantoms to measure noise reduction,
 371 sharpness, and low contrast detectability across a range of pediatric subgroups (Table 1). Consistent with
 372 previous findings, we found that the baseline RED-CNN model (Figure 1a) showed a strong trend in noise
 373 reduction and detectability with phantom size,¹⁰ however we found that the augmented RED-CNN
 374 model (Figure 1b) performed more consistently across all pediatric subgroup sizes (Figure 6). This
 375 improved noise reduction in smaller patient sizes also resulted in improved low contrast detectability
 376 (Figure 8). While this study investigated the impact of noise texture augmentation using a single RED-

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

377 CNN model architecture, this training technique to improve pediatric generalizability focuses on adding
378 variability to the training dataset. While absolute denoising and image quality performance may vary
379 with different model architectures, the overall conclusions that incorporating pediatric noise textures
380 into model training positively impacts generalizability broadly applies to other architectures.

381 In the present study the augmentation strength parameter λ was defined as a scalar between 0 and 1
382 setting the proportion of augmented inputs in each training batch with the remainder consisting of the
383 original adult dataset inputs. This parameter λ controls the strength of the augmentation and in this
384 initial investigation was selected such that the denoised image noise magnitude measured in a
385 validation set of pediatric phantom images was like the routine dose noise magnitude in adult images.
386 Future work aims at redefining this augmentation scalar as a vector of weights controlling the relative
387 contribution of size-specific noise images (Figure 2). This size-specific augmentation approach would
388 enable further fine tuning of the denoised output noise magnitude and texture for specific size-based
389 subgroups.

390 Data augmentation can impute missing variability of data if that variability can be modeled. In the
391 present study, this missing variability was the wider range of pediatric body sizes than is typically
392 encompassed by adult datasets because pediatrics is large and diverse population ranging from
393 newborns through adolescents (*Table 1*). As pediatric abdomen imaging protocols recommend body
394 fitting fields-of-view (FOVs), this results in distinct, often lower frequency noise textures due to the
395 smaller resulting voxel sizes than in adult images.¹⁰ In this initial approach, we demonstrated how
396 imaging different sized phantoms with varying FOV was sufficient to incorporate this patient and FOV
397 size variability into denoising model training. This approach of using phantom data to add more size and
398 FOV variability is different than previous phantom-based training approaches which focused on the use
399 of phantoms to create more high and low dose image pairs for model training.²⁵ Similarly, other data
400 augmentation has been pursued in different applications, such as computer aided detection, to improve
401 generalizability to different dose levels.¹¹

402 While patient size is one major difference between pediatrics and adults, there are many other
403 anatomic, pathologic, and imaging protocol differences that vary with pediatric development, such as
404 visceral and subcutaneous fat content. Investigating which differences most impact deep learning model
405 performance and which applications are most sensitive to these differences can better inform the
406 design of medical devices based on AI/ML. This informed design could include more specific dataset
407 curation emphasizing inclusion of certain patient variability such as size investigated previously, or
408 model training techniques such as noise texture augmentation introduced here, to incorporate that
409 variability when diverse patient data is unavailable.

410 5 CONCLUSION

411 Pediatric data for deep learning (DL) model development is and will likely remain scarce, thus without
412 investing in developing large diverse pediatric datasets for different applications, pediatric patients will
413 continue to be disadvantaged by or excluded from the latest advancements in medical care made
414 possible by artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) powered medical devices. This study
415 introduces a stopgap alternative to retrain existing deep learning CT denoising models with existing
416 adult datasets using phantom data augmentation until such diverse pediatric datasets are available.

417 Using a previously validated pediatric denoising assessment framework we demonstrated both with
418 simulation and physical scan data that this approach can be effective at improving denoising image
419 quality performance in smaller pediatric patients. This work further demonstrates the need to
420 characterize the performance of AI/ML devices in pediatric patients that could benefit. Furthermore,
421 this study provides an example of how better understanding where these devices are most sensitive to
422 unique pediatric characteristics enables better design of devices to make more efficient use of limited
423 pediatric data.

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427 7 CONFLICT OF INTEREST

428 The authors of this work have no conflicts of interest to disclose related to this work.

429 8 DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

430 Code used to generate the figures used in this study can be found at
431 <https://github.com/brandonjnelsonFDA/pediatric-CT-noise-texture-augmentation> and from the
432 corresponding author upon reasonable request.

433 9 REFERENCES

- 434 1. Health C for D and R. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML)-Enabled Medical Devices.
435 FDA. Published online October 5, 2022. Accessed January 24, 2023. [https://www.fda.gov/medical-](https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/software-medical-device-samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-aiml-enabled-medical-devices)
436 [devices/software-medical-device-samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-aiml-enabled-](https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/software-medical-device-samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-aiml-enabled-medical-devices)
437 [medical-devices](https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/software-medical-device-samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-aiml-enabled-medical-devices)
- 438 2. Nelson BJ, Zeng R, Sammer M, Frush DP, Delfino JG. An FDA Guide on Indications for Use and Device
439 Reporting of Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Devices: Significance for Pediatric Use. *Journal of the*
440 *American College of Radiology*. Published online July 1, 2023. doi:10.1016/j.jacr.2023.06.004
- 441 3. Sammer MBK, Akbari YS, Barth RA, et al. Use of Artificial Intelligence in Radiology: Impact on Pediatric
442 Patients, a White Paper From the ACR Pediatric AI Workgroup. *Journal of the American College of*
443 *Radiology*. Published online July 25, 2023. doi:10.1016/j.jacr.2023.06.003
- 444 4. Don S, MacDougall R, Strauss K, et al. Image Gently Campaign Back to Basics Initiative: Ten Steps to
445 Help Manage Radiation Dose in Pediatric Digital Radiography. *American Journal of Roentgenology*.
446 2013;200(5):W431-W436. doi:10.2214/AJR.12.9895
- 447 5. Brady SL. Implementation of AI image reconstruction in CT-how is it validated and what dose
448 reductions can be achieved. *Br J Radiol*. 2023;96(1150):20220915. doi:10.1259/bjr.20220915

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

- 449 6. Brady SL, Trout AT, Somasundaram E, Anton CG, Li Y, Dillman JR. Improving Image Quality and
450 Reducing Radiation Dose for Pediatric CT by Using Deep Learning Reconstruction. *Radiology*.
451 2021;298(1):180-188. doi:10.1148/radiol.2020202317
- 452 7. Moen TR, Chen B, Holmes III DR, et al. Low-dose CT image and projection dataset. *Medical Physics*.
453 2021;48(2):902-911. doi:10.1002/mp.14594
- 454 8. Huber NR, Missert AD, Yu L, Leng S, McCollough CH. Evaluating a Convolutional Neural Network Noise
455 Reduction Method When Applied to CT Images Reconstructed Differently Than Training Data. *Journal*
456 *of Computer Assisted Tomography*. 2021; Publish Ahead of Print.
457 doi:10.1097/RCT.0000000000001150
- 458 9. Zeng R, Lin CY, Li Q, et al. Performance of a deep learning-based CT image denoising method:
459 Generalizability over dose, reconstruction kernel, and slice thickness. *Med Phys*. 2022;49(2):836-853.
460 doi:10.1002/mp.15430
- 461 10. Nelson BJ, Kc P, Badal A, Jiang L, Masters SC, Zeng R. Pediatric evaluations for deep learning CT
462 denoising. *Medical Physics*. 2024;51(2):978-990. doi:10.1002/mp.16901
- 463 11. McIntosh J, Cao Q, Sahiner B, Petrick N, Farhangi MM. DICaugment: A Python Package for 3D
464 Medical Imaging Augmentation. *Journal of Open Source Software*. 2024;9(95):6120.
465 doi:10.21105/joss.06120
- 466 12. Chen H, Zhang Y, Kalra MK, et al. Low-Dose CT With a Residual Encoder-Decoder Convolutional
467 Neural Network. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*. 2017;36(12):2524-2535.
468 doi:10.1109/TMI.2017.2715284
- 469 13. Yu L, Shiung M, Jondal D, McCollough CH. Development and Validation of a Practical Lower-
470 Dose-Simulation Tool for Optimizing Computed Tomography Scan Protocols. *Journal of Computer*
471 *Assisted Tomography*. 2012;36(4):477-487. doi:10.1097/RCT.0b013e318258e891
- 472 14. Health C for D and R. Premarket Assessment of Pediatric Medical Devices. U.S. Food and Drug
473 Administration. Published March 24, 2020. Accessed March 1, 2023.
474 [https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/premarket-](https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/premarket-assessment-pediatric-medical-devices)
475 [assessment-pediatric-medical-devices](https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/premarket-assessment-pediatric-medical-devices)
- 476 15. McCollough C, Bakalyar D, Bostani M, et al. *Use of Water Equivalent Diameter for Calculating*
477 *Patient Size and Size-Specific Dose Estimates (SSDE) in CT*. AAPM; 2014. doi:10.37206/146
- 478 16. Segars WP, Norris H, Sturgeon GM, et al. The development of a population of 4D pediatric XCAT
479 phantoms for imaging research and optimization. *Med Phys*. 2015;42(8):4719-4726.
480 doi:10.1118/1.4926847
- 481 17. McCollough CH, Bartley AC, Carter RE, et al. Low-dose CT for the detection and classification of
482 metastatic liver lesions: Results of the 2016 Low Dose CT Grand Challenge. *Med Phys*.
483 2017;44(10):e339-e352. doi:10.1002/mp.12345

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

- 484 18. Kc P, Zeng R, Farhangi MM, Myers KJ. Deep neural networks-based denoising models for CT
485 imaging and their efficacy. In: Bosmans H, Zhao W, Yu L, eds. *Medical Imaging 2021: Physics of*
486 *Medical Imaging*. SPIE; 2021:16. doi:10.1117/12.2581418
- 487 19. Friedman SN, Fung GSK, Siewerdsen JH, Tsui BMW. A simple approach to measure computed
488 tomography (CT) modulation transfer function (MTF) and noise-power spectrum (NPS) using the
489 American College of Radiology (ACR) accreditation phantom. *Medical Physics*. 2013;40(5):051907.
490 doi:10.1118/1.4800795
- 491 20. Gallas BD, Barrett HH. Validating the use of channels to estimate the ideal linear observer. *J Opt*
492 *Soc Am A*. 2003;20(9):1725. doi:10.1364/JOSAA.20.001725
- 493 21. Abbey CK, Barrett HH. Human- and model-observer performance in ramp-spectrum noise:
494 effects of regularization and object variability. *J Opt Soc Am A, JOSAA*. 2001;18(3):473-488.
495 doi:10.1364/JOSAA.18.000473
- 496 22. Fessler JA. Michigan Image Reconstruction Toolbox. Accessed November 10, 2023.
497 <https://web.eecs.umich.edu/~fessler/code/index.html>
- 498 23. AAPM CT Scan Protocols - The Alliance for Quality Computed Tomography. Accessed June 29,
499 2023. <https://www.aapm.org/pubs/ctprotocols/default.asp?tab=5#CTabbedPanels>
- 500 24. Vaishnav JY, Jung WC, Popescu LM, Zeng R, Myers KJ. Objective assessment of image quality and
501 dose reduction in CT iterative reconstruction. *Med Phys*. 2014;41(7):071904. doi:10.1118/1.4881148
- 502 25. Huber NR, Missert AD, Gong H, Leng S, Yu L, McCollough CH. Technical note: Phantom-based
503 training framework for convolutional neural network CT noise reduction. *Medical Physics*.
504 2023;50(2):821-830. doi:10.1002/mp.16093

505 **10 FIGURE LEGENDS**

506 *Figure 1 Schematic diagrams of image-based deep learning CT denoising model training. (a) Traditional model training where*
507 *training input patches are input to a model to make a prediction that is compared against the training target using the loss*
508 *function to update the model. (b) In noise texture augmented training noise patches are added to the low noise training target*
509 *to make new augmented inputs. While training, a proportion λ of the training data mini batch is from the augmented inputs*
510 *while the remaining $1 - \lambda$ is from the original low dose training inputs. LD = Low dose, FD = Full dose CT acquisitions.*

511 *Figure 2 Noise patch generation for noise texture augmentation. a) Summary of size-specific noise patch generation which starts*
512 *with collecting phantoms of diameter spanning the range of expected pediatric size (Table 1), these phantoms are scanned*
513 *repeatedly with tube current modulation to achieve similar noise indices in different phantom sizes and reconstructed with body*
514 *fitting fields of view (FOV) b). Subtracting the consecutive repeat scans yields size-specific noise images c.). Histogram matching*
515 *the phantom noise images to the training set noise images d) – found by taking the difference of a sample of matched low dose*
516 *and high dose training patches – ensures that the augmented inputs (Figure 1) have the same noise magnitude as the low dose*
517 *training inputs. The result are noise patches of similar noise magnitude as the training set but with range of noise textures*
518 *represented by noise power peaks at different spatial frequencies e).*

519 *Figure 3 Selection of λ value from a central region of interest (ROI) standard deviation (std) measurement averaged across*
520 *pediatric-sized uniform water phantom images from the validation dataset.*

Noise Texture Augmentation for CT Denoising

- 521 *Figure 4 CT simulations of XCAT anthropomorphic phantoms of different effective diameter reconstructed with Filtered back*
522 *projection (FBP) followed by denoising with different deep learning denoising models. Region of interest (ROI) measurements,*
523 *shown as blue disk overlays, taken from the liver report pixel mean and standard deviation with the ROI.*
- 524 *Figure 5 Denoising efficiency as a function of phantom size with body fitting reconstructed field of view (FOV). a) Noise reduction*
525 *performance defined as reduction of pixel intensity standard deviation (std) relative to filtered backprojection (fbp): noise std*
526 *reduction [%] = [fbp std - denoised std]/fbp std × 100%. Noise in uniform phantoms is measured in central circular regions of*
527 *interest (ROIs) 40% the phantom diameter. In anthropomorphic phantoms, the ROI size was set at 30% phantom effective*
528 *diameter and only applied to slices where there was enough liver to fit the ROI, see Figure 4 for examples. b) Noise reduction*
529 *performance defined as reduction in root mean squared error (rmse) with the ground truth simulated phantom: rmse reduction*
530 *[%] = [fbp rmse - denoised rmse]/fbp rmse × 100%. RMSE reduction is measured across the whole image.*
- 531 *Figure 6 Denoising performance measured as pixel intensity standard deviation (std) measured in liver regions of interest (ROIs)*
532 *from anthropomorphic phantoms. The ROI size was set at 30% phantom effective diameter and only applied to slices where*
533 *there was enough liver to fit the ROI, see Figure 4 for examples. Pediatric subgroups are based on the waist diameters defined in*
534 *Table 2.*
- 535 *Figure 7 Image sharpness evaluated as 50% and 10% cutoff frequencies of modulation transfer function (MTF) measured from*
536 *radially averaged disk measurements at different contrast levels, shown as the title of each plot. Average MTF cutoffs values are*
537 *shown for each pediatric subgroup based on phantom diameter (Table 1) with error bars representing the 95% bootstrap*
538 *confidence interval.*
- 539 *Figure 8 Low contrast detectability area under the receiver operator characteristic curve (AUC) as a function of phantom*
540 *diameter from quarter dose test images. Detectability is assessed using two model observers: a Laguerre-Gauss Channelized*
541 *Hotelling observer (LG-CHO) and a non-prewhitening (NPW) observer. The 3 HU contrast lesion has a diameter of 10% the*
542 *phantom diameter and the 14 HU diameter is 5% the phantom diameter.*
- 543 *Figure 9 Physical image quality (IQ) phantom scan validation experiment. a) Uniform region for noise assessment in physical*
544 *ACR464 phantom scanned on a Siemens Edge Plus scanner (see Table 2 for details). b) ACR phantom reconstructed at 3 fields of*
545 *view (FOVs) estimating adult, child, and infant scan conditions. c) Simulated images of uniform phantom defined at adult, child,*
546 *and newborn size. d) Comparison of noise reduction trends measured in physical and simulated images.*